

**Experimental base of "N.Pushkarov" Institute of
Soil Science Agrotechnologies and Plant
Protection - Tsalapitsa village, Plovdiv region
First experiment**

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Results of the first experiments on Tsalapitsa village, Plovdiv region test field

Tsalapitsa 48 plots - Runoff plots (48 plots 40 m² each)

Latitude (WGS84); decimal degree (+: North, -:South)- 42°11' 42.183333

Longitude (WGS84); decimal degree (+: East, -: West)- 24°33' 24.55

the length of the observation (available data), from-to (year)- 1994-till the present

plots/design of the experiment-Runoff plots (48 plots 40 m² each)

FARMING SYTEM, main-conventional farming

main crop-annual crops

tillage method-minimum tillage; Balance of the elements; Nitrate washing; Long term runoff plot experiment

Tsalapitsa 30plots

Type of the site- experiment/plots

the length of the observation (available data), from-to (year)- since 1972 till the present

plots/design of the experiment- Runoff plots (30 plots 201,6 m² each)

FARMING SYTEM, main-conventional farming

Tsalapitsa 16plots

plots/design of the experiment- randomized block design with 4 treatments and 4 reps. (16 plots 201,6 m² each);

short description of the site- Long term runoff plot experiment

Climatic characteristics of the experimental base Tsalapitsa

Tsalapitsa is located in the climatic region of Eastern Central Bulgaria. The winter is relatively mild - the average temperature in January is around 0°C, soil temperatures at a depth of 2 and 5 cm in January are distinguished by relatively high values - 1.5 - 1.8°C. Precipitation in winter averages 115 mm, but only about 30-35% of it is from snow. Climatic characteristics of the experimental base Tsalapitsa.

Thanks to the rapid rise in temperatures at the end of the mild winter here, spring starts early. The average starting date with sustained retention of temperatures above 5°C occurs around 5.III., and above 10°C – on 4.IV. Soil temperatures at a depth of 10 cm in March reach 7.3 °C, and in April they are already 13.5 °C. The average date of the last frost is 4.IV. The sowing of spring crops in this area can begin at the end of the first ten days of April.

Summer is warm, with the average July temperature being 23.2oC, and the number of days with an average daily air temperature above 25oC is more than twenty. The temperature sum for the period with average daily temperatures above 10°C is 3795° – sufficient for the development of crops with a longer growing season. The annual amount of precipitation is small - 515 mm, with 240 mm of precipitation falling in the period April-August, and the deficit in the atmospheric moisture balance is 200-250 mm.

Various researches are being carried out, developed under projects, which in recent years are as follows:

1. Agroecological approaches to optimize the nutritional regime of agricultural crops

Agroecological assessment of the soil-chemical and nutritional status of cereals in the conditions of cultivated alluvial-meadow soil.

Field experiments with corn (*Zea mays*, L.) on alluvial-meadow soil in OP Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv Region, were planted and carried out in the experimental field. During the maize growing season, phenological observations were made and a number of biometric indicators were recorded. The growth dynamics of absolutely dry biomass in two phenophases was monitored, the leaf area index was calculated, and the content of leaf pigments was determined. Significant correlations were found between the investigated parameters and yield. It was reported that the highest maize yield was obtained from the variants T2 (N₁₆P₁₂) and from those with the maximum T3 (N₂₀P₁₆) fertilization rate.

The state of the main macrolelements in the soil (mineral nitrogen, absorbable forms of phosphorus and potassium) and the soil reaction before and after the experiment was evaluated. The addition of the database with scientific information obtained as a result of the Polish experiment, necessary for an ecological assessment of modern land use methods, continued. Quantitative parameters for characterizing the liquid phase of the soil were obtained.

The chemical composition of precipitation and shallow groundwater was analyzed and the income of the main macrolelements with them was calculated. The volume of drainage runoff at two depths was determined and the export of chemical elements with lysimeter waters during corn cultivation was calculated. It was established that the export of nitrate nitrogen, depending on the fertilization rates, ranges from 0.13 to 2.04 kg.da⁻¹, and the export of calcium reaches 5.25 kg.da⁻¹. Significant correlations were established between the content of nitrogen imported with fertilizers and the export of nitrates, calcium and magnesium with lysimeter waters.

The evaluation of the efficiency of the applied fertilizers shows that the agronomic efficiency coefficient of nitrogen is the lowest in the maximally fertilized variant, while the responsiveness of the culture to nitrogen fertilization is the greatest in the variants with the lower fertilizer rates. Research on the environmental monitoring of groundwater to study the relationships and trends between the loading of urbanized areas and the condition of the waters and their quality has continued.

2. Influence of biochar coal in combination with nitrogen fertilizer on the volume density and porosity of alluvial meadow soil

In an experimental field in the village of Tsalapitsa, a field experiment was carried out with corn to study the change in the stability of the soil structure under the influence of the combined introduction of biochar from oak bark at 400°C (0, 10 and 20 t/ha) with nitrogen fertilization (130 and 260 kg) /ha). A significant and statistically significant increase in water-resistant aggregates of size 3-1 mm and soil layer 0-40 cm was found in both the second and third year of application of 5 t/ha biochar with 130 kg/ha nitrogen fertilizer.

At this rate of nitrogen fertilization, the introduction of 10 t/ha of biochar has a stronger effect in the second than in the third year of its introduction. Similar regularities are also observed in the variants with 260 kg/ha of nitrogen fertilizer, but the effect of the application of biochar is significant only in the third year of the introduction of 5 t/ha. The water resistance of the soil structure, assessed by the water resistance index (Sd/Sw), shows similar trends as the rest of the studied structural indicators.

3. Influence of crop rotation on the export of nitrogen with lysimetric waters in vulnerable zones

Research was conducted on an experimental field in Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv on Alluvial-meadow soil (Fluvisol). In the field crop rotation experiment (maize-wheat), three variants with increasing rates of nitrogen and phosphorus are tested, which are compared with a variant without fertilization. The experiment was carried out with grain maize (*Zea mays*, L.) FAO group 310, with fertilization rates (T0 N₀P₀; T1 N₁₂P₈; T2 N₁₆P₁₂; T3 N₂₀P₁₆). After corn, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) was grown, with the following fertilization options - (T0 N₀P₀; T1 N₁₀P₆; T2 N₁₄P₁₀; T3 N₁₈P₁₄)

The scheme of the experiment is adapted to pre-installed lysimeter devices of the Ebermeyer type, at a depth of 0-100 cm from the soil surface. The volume of lysimeter waters was calculated, the nitrogen content and its export with the leachate were analyzed. It was found that after the vegetation of corn, the volume of lysimeter waters reaches 75.95 l.m², while after wheat, the resulting drainage is about 2.5-3 times lower. The nitrogen content, depending on the fertilization rates after corn, is in the range from 10.8 to 37.5 mg.l⁻¹, and for wheat in the range from 8.73 to 23.58 mg.l⁻¹.

The exports of the element with the drainage runoff with the first crop are respectively – 0.56- 2.85 kg.da⁻¹, and with wheat – 0.12-0.63 kg.da⁻¹. It is established that when growing crops with the fusion surface, the export of nitrate nitrogen outside the root-inhabited soil layer is significantly reduced.

4. Dynamics of accumulation of absolutely dry biomass of corn as dependence on applied fertilization of alluvial meadow soil

The research aims to evaluate the effect of the interaction between different rates and combinations of fertilization with nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and silicon fertilizers on the development of maize (*Zea mays* L.) mid-early hybrid P-8834 "Pioneer" from group 310 FAO. The Polish experience was produced in the experimental base Tsalapitsa of "N. Pushkarov" Institute of Soil Science Agrotechnologies and Plant Protection, Plovdiv region, on alluvial-meadow soil (Fluvisol, FAO).

The study included 8 fertilization variants and one control variant, which allowed the evaluation of the actions and interactions of more than three factors varying at three levels in 3 replications. Data from agrochemical soil analyzes were used for the content of the basic nutrients available to plants in the soil.

The amount of absolute dry matter in the biomass of 1 plant was studied by stages of corn development - 9-10 leaf, milk maturity and the harvest yield was reported. It was established that the amount of absolute dry matter in the biomass by stages of corn development was significantly influenced by the applied rates and combinations of fertilizers. In the 9-10 leaf stage of maize, the highest mean values of leaf and stem biomass were obtained in variant 4 (N₂₀₀P₁₆₀K₆₀Si₁₄). In the milk maturity phase, the sum of the average values of leaves and stems is the highest in variant 7 (N₁₀₀P₁₆₀K₁₂₀Si₂₈) - 310.73 g per plant.

Established trends in plant biomass during the corn growing season correlate with corn yield data. With the different fertilization options and combinations, corn yields are two to three times higher than the non-fertilized option, with a very well-proven statistical difference. In conclusion, the leading role of nitrogen stands out in variants with high rates of nitrogen, low levels of potassium and silica. To establish the mutual influence of the combinations of silicon with other macroelements on the studied parameters, longer studies

in the conditions of Polish experiments are necessary, because the climatic conditions during the year have a significant influence.